

THE OPEN SPACE, HUMAN RESOURCE AND PUBLIC PARTICIPATION - PART OF SPORT DEVELOPMENT IN WONOGIRI REGENCY, INDONESIA

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Abstract:

Sport Development in a region cannot be measured only based on one indicator of medal achievement in multi-event competition, but can be done by measuring open space, human resource (HR) and the public participation in doing sport activities. Although it's a simple thing, but it will give the right information about long term development clearly, especially in sport sector which is more relatable with other development sectors. The purpose of this research was investigating the index of open space, the index of HR and the index of public participation. Technique of sampling in the research used Stratified random sampling with cluster sampling and the amount of the sample is 270 people. The research used evaluation method. The technique of collecting Data used observation, questioner, and document. The result of the research showed the amount of the index of open space was 0,711, the index of HR was 0.0010, and the index of public participation was 0,237. The conclusion of this research is Wonogiri Regency have enough open space for sport but has few HR of sport. This describes that the Wonogiri still in great need of human resources involved in sport will be able to develop and promote the potential of sport in Wonogiri. Meanwhile, the public participation in Wonogiri Regency in doing sport is very less; there are only 0,237 people in Wonogiri Regency who participate in sport, minimum three times a week, although they are provided good enough open space. It means that sports development Wonogiri is far from developed. Many things need to be considered and addressed by the government to promote sports development in Wonogiri.

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1. Introduction

Development is a programmed effort that is done continuously to maintain and improve human's life level, both physically and psychically. Development cannot be separated from the growth, which means that development can cause the happen of growth. In this case, the growth can be expansion, or improvement from the activities of a people community. Systematic effort for expansion which is released in synergic power has been done in the development of all sectors, includes sport development. Although there are many achievements that have been received in sport sector, actually there are still many things lack in effort of sport development in our country, moreover it can be said that the success is not balance with the potential.

Through the systematic sport training, human resource can be directed for improving self-control, responsibility, discipline, high level of sporty which contains transfer's value for other sectors. Based on the characteristics, finally it can be gotten improvement sport's achievement that can totally rises national proud and defense. Nowadays, the focus of sport development is to civilize and improve sport achievement. If we put a relation to sport building, it means that the strengthening of sport building foundation is sport culture and the strengthening of sport achievement's seedling pattern. It has a purpose to create a huge amount of talented prospective athlete from many regions of Indonesia which is suitable with the physical character, local culture, and the environment's condition that supports the formation of sport potentials in the regions.

Measuring the level of people sport development is not only done by one indicator, medal achievement, but it can also be done by measuring Indonesian sport development through the SDI (Sport Development Index). SDI is the instrument to measure the result of sport development in region. SDI is the new concept that released after published reports about human's development in all countries around the world that had been issued by UNDP (United National Development programme). It is a united nation's organization that works in the development sector.

SDI is expected to determine the level of sport progress in a region. Because of that, the creation of competition climate in sport development can be directed to basic nature sport development, not in an instant such as medal achievements. According to Cholik and Maksum (2007), SDI is the combined index that reflecting the success of sport development based on four basic dimensions: (1) Open space that provided for sport, (2) Human Resource or athletes who have been involved in sport activity, (3) the

society's participations to do regular sport and (4) Physical health that can be reached by the people. The focus of the research was related to four open space's dimensions and the public participation. The open space was determined based on criteria: (1) used for sport activity, (2) purposely designed to sport activity, and (3) can be accessed by wide community. Human resource dimension refers to the amount of sports coaches, teachers Physical and Health Education and sports instructor in a particular region. Participation dimension is based on how many community members in a region who do sport activity. Open space dimension is based on how large the place which is used to sport activity for the people in a land or building.

One of region in Indonesia which has a potential to create prospective athlete is Wonogiri regency. Several problems that should be faced in sport achievement civilizing and training in Wonogiri regency are educational sport sector, special sport school in wonogiri which is still limited, the lack of personnel in sport who understand about the system of early age sport training, and the facilities and infrastructures which is not good enough. For that reason, the government tries to improve sport activity through the school training or sport club. It is expected to create good prospective athletes. The achievement can make national proud increased and also it can be calculated as measurement of region progress.

2. Materials and Method

This research is an evaluation study about sport development. The technique of collecting data used observation, questioner, and document. The research has been done in Wonogiri regency in September until December 2016. The technique of sampling used stratified random sampling with cluster sampling with the number of sample was 270 people which consist of the people from Wonogiri district, Bulukerto district, and Pracimantoro district. The researcher took 90 people from every district who had been divided into 3 age stages, they are 30 people of children (7-12 years old), 30 people from teenagers (13-17 years old), and 30 people of adult (18-40 years old) that consist of 15 male and 15 female. After getting the result of open space index, Human Resource (HR) and public participation index, then the researcher determined index level based on SDI norm table as followed:

Table 1: SDI NORM

The number of index	Norm / categories
0,800 – 1,000	High
0,500 – 0,799	Medium
0,000 – 0,499	Low

(Kristiyanto, 2012)

3. Result of the Research and Discussion

a. Open Space in Wonogiri Regency

Open space is a space or room which can be used to sport for the public both indoor and outdoor. The number of open space that been measured based on open space ratio in a region with the number of society in age 7 years old and more. Open space standard that been adopted by Olympic committee is 3.5 m and minimum score is 0 m. The formula that can be used to get the number of open space index is:

$$Open\ space\ index = \frac{Actual\ score - Minimum\ score}{Maximum\ score - Minimum\ score}$$

(Kristiyanto, 2012)

Based on the result of open space in three districts, sample that has been gotten described the index of public sport room in Wonogiri regency as followed:

Table 2: The score of index of public sport room in Wonogiri regency

Number.	Name of District	Score the index of open space
1.	Wonogiri District	0,845
2.	Bulukerto district	0,685
3.	Pracimantoro district	0,603
The index of open space in Wonogiri regency		0,711

The score of public sport room index in Wonogiri regency that had been got from 3 districts which has been researched is 0.711. Based on the SDI norm, Wonogiri Regency is in the medium category. There are 711 people of 1000 people in Wonogiri regency who had been provided the open space for sport. It is because there are many government's facilities which is used for sport and the people creativity to use empty land for sport room. In addition, many sports facilities and infrastructure private property that is accessible by the general society such as the pool, futsal court and fitness center.

Despite the availability of open space Wonogiri enough good, but not yet meet the standards of open space ideal adopted by the Olympic Committee was set at 3.5 m per person, if the comparison between the availability of open space with a population of over 7 years in Wonogiri The results show the index value of open space Wonogiri in the position of moderate / medium when compared to the norm Sport Developmet index (SDI).

Still need the attention of the government to expand the open space of sport for society that fulfilled the needs of physical activity that is equal to 0.299. Besides equity in the construction of sports facilities and infrastructure in each district is also worth noting that there is the potential of sports which can be developed to the fullest.

b. Human Resource (HR)

HR index is measured by the ratio of amount of of HR sport with a population over the age of 7 years. The maximum value that has been determined SDI is the minimum value of 2.08 and 0.00. To get the index value of human resources using the following formula:

$$Open\ space\ index = \frac{Actual\ score - Minimum\ score}{Maximum\ score - Minimum\ score}$$

(Kristiyanto, 2012)

Based on the results of the index of human resources (HR) sports in three sub samples were obtained an average which is the data for human resources (HR) in Wonogiri as follows:

Table 3: The index of HR in Wonogiri Regency

No	Name of District	Score the index of HR
1	Wonogiri district	0,0013
2	Bulukerto district	0,0009
3	Pracimantoro district	0,0008
The index of HR in Wonogiri Regency		0.0010

HR index Wonogiri obtained from an average of 3 sub-district have been studied which is equal to 0.0010. Values of this index lower than the index of national human resources in 2006 is equal to 0.099. When viewed from the norm sport developmet index (SDI) index is still far short of the 0.499, it means that human resources (HR) sports in Wonogiri is included in the low category. In quantity and quality of human resources is not adequate Wonogiri sport.

This describes that the Wonogiri still in great need of human resources involved in sport will be able to develop and promote the potential of sport in Wonogiri. Fonemena is affected because of the many sports that man has a dual role, in the sense that a lot of teachers who doubles as the club's coach, a referee, as a teacher of extracurricular and there is also an instructor. In addition, there are some people who have a certificate in Wonogiri but not develop their knowledge in the field of sports but in other areas of life which they are able to provide their livelihood and their families.

Required special attention from the government regarding the availability of human sport in Wonogiri. One effort that can be done is to establish cooperation with the provincial government in conducting license coaches, referees and instructors, increase income for those who have been active in the field of sports, providing scholarships for children Wonogiri with competence sport to continue on to higher education and required back to their hometown after graduation. It is expected the HR sport in Wonogiri increased with the presence of population

c. Public participation

To know about public participation in Wonogiri is by giving questioners. Sport participation basically divided into two kinds. They are common participation and special participation. Sport participation commonly can be done directly and indirectly. Direct sport participation means people directly doing sport involving their physical. Meanwhile indirect sport participation is a sport which been done indirectly and not involved with physical activities such as event organizer sponsor, sport industry/ sport room rental/ and sport equipment providing.

Special participation is about getting involved directly and actively as sport people. Sport can be formal such as achievement sport, and informal such as traditional sport, and also it can be recreational, competitive, and fitness sport. These kind of sport is done in family, society, and also in educational environment that usually called by physical education.

Participation score was measured based on ratio between the participant and the amount of population in age 7 years old and more when the research was done. People sport participation is based on sport frequents which has been done minimum three times a week. The formula to get the index of public participation is as followed with the maximum score is 100 and the minimum score is 0.

$$\text{The index of participation} = \frac{\text{Actual Score} - \text{Minimum Score}}{\text{Maximum Score} - \text{Minimum Score}}$$

(Kristiyanto, 2012)

The collecting data of sport participation in Wonogiri reGENCY used three sample districts. They are Wonogiri district, Bulukerto district, and Purwantoro district. Every district was taken 90 samples to be given questioner about sport participation. The sample was categorized based on age. They are 30 Children in age 7 – 12 years old, 30 teenagers in age 13 -17 years old, and 30 people in adult category with age 18 – 40 years old. 30 adult are 15 male samples and 15 female samples. The determination of the sample is as followed:

Table 4: Public participation Sample to Sport

Categories District	Children (7-12 years old)	Adolescence (13-17 years old)	Adult (18-40 years old)
Wonogiri distric	SDN 1 Wonogiri	SMAN 2 Wonogiri	Bulusulur Village
Bulukerto distric	SDN 2 Krandegan	SMKN 1 Bulukerto	Conto Village
Pracimantoro distric	SDN 1 Jimbar	SMKN 1 Pracimantoro	Pracimantoro Village

Based on three sport participation index from three districts which had been used as sample, it can be known that the average which showed the index of public participation in doing sport in Wonogiri reGENCY is as followed:

Table 5: Public participation Index of Wonogiri reGENCY

Number	Name of districts	Participation Index
1.	Wonogiri District	0,300
2.	Bulukerto District	0,211
3.	Pracimantoro District	0,200
Sport participation index in Wonogiri reGENCY		0,237

Based on the table above, public participation index in Wonogiri reGENCY showed the score 0.237. If it is seen based on Sport Development Index (SDI), this score is still far from score 0.499. It means that public participation in Wonogiri reGENCY is in Low category. From 1000 people, there are only 237 people in Wonogiri reGENCY doing sport minimum three times a week. This indicates that people Wonogiri have awareness for exercise is low, not only because of internal factors of the community such as do not have time to exercise because of work, exhausted after doing daily activities, and is also caused by external factors is not yet fully in facilitating well by the availability of open space sport and also the availability of human sports.

The government should conduct public education about the benefits of exercise for health and also the effect of exercise on other areas of life. Offset by the establishment of policies that lead to make people do sport and promote sports. It is

expected there will be awareness from within each community to participate in sports. Sport is expected to be a need for the people, the government stays to keep the rhythm and encourage people fond of exercise in order to create the sports culture as the foundation of achievement.

4. Conclusion

Based on the result of research above, it can be concluded that sport development in Wonogiri Regency is in low category. Although there are many achievements that have been received by the Wonogiri's athletes, but the basic thing that have been used as foundation to answer the question about how many medals that have been received in multi events competition is related to open space, human resource (HR) and public participation in Wonogiri regency to do sport cannot be done properly.

From the result of the research, it showed the index of open space in Wonogiri regency is 0.711. It means that from 1000 people in Wonogiri regency, there are 711 people who have been provided enough open space for doing sport. Meanwhile, the index of public participation is 0.237 which means that public participation in Wonogiri regency is in low category. From 1000 people, there are only 237 people doing sport minimum three times a week. The provision of good open spaces cannot make people in Wonogiri regency has enthusiasm to use the facilities to do sport, even though there are many benefits that can be got from doing sport to body health and physical health in common. Physical health is a basic factor for someone to do daily activities without getting much tired.

HR index is the most low at 0.0010, which means that the availability of human sports such as physical education teachers, coaches, referees and sports instructors still lacking. The need for cooperation between Disbudparpora, the Department of Education and Sports Committee in creating a policy to increase the availability of human sport in Wonogiri Regency as an effort to increase the development of sports. Nevertheless, the two other dimensions that cannot be ignored anyway given the open space, human resources, public participation is an indicator of the success of the development of sport in an area that is interconnected between the indicator with other indicators.

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